

half $\bar{n}$ method⁶. Refinement of the approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was done by different computational methods⁸. The results thus obtained are summarized in Table I in which the values of overall free energy changes accompanying the complexation reactions have also been included.

It is evident from the data presented in Table I that the stability constants of these complexes are in the order $UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Co > Zn > Cd$, which is in agreement with the Irving and Williams rule⁹.

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Some Crystal Field Surface Orbital—Bond Energy Bond Order (CFSO-BEBO) Calculations of Heats of Adsorption of Hydrogen on Nickel Methanation Catalysts

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THE production of methane on nickel catalyst has gained an impetus in recent years on account of its importance in the production of S.N.G. (synthetic natural gas). For example, a methane synthesis unit has been attached to Westfield Lurgi Plant¹ for enrichment of the gas produced by the high pressure process.

Some adsorption studies of hydrogen on nickel catalyst were carried out, and a few isosteric heats of adsorption calculated by the author² some years ago. The advent of crystal field surface orbital bond energy bond order (CFSO-BEBO) model³ has facilitated the theoretical calculation of heats of adsorption. Although the calculations lack the usefulness of other theoretical treatments, such as Extended Huckel⁴, they nevertheless provide a simple theoretical model (involving as they do a combination of crystal field theory, crystal symmetry and Born-Haber Cycle concepts) which is able to explain experimental results. The heats of adsorption (both molecular and chemisorption) of hydrogen on platinum calculated by the CFSO-BEBO procedure have been found to agree very well with those

determined experimentally. Further, the variation of heat of adsorption as a function of coverage has been placed on a theoretical basis.

The catalysts, based on nickel were prepared by precipitation on Kieselguhr from solutions of their nitrates. They had the composition given below :

Catalyst C : Nickel : Thoria : Kieselguhr
: : 100 : 18 : 100.

Catalyst D : Nickel : Thoria : Chromium Oxide :
Kieselguhr : : 100 : 9 : 9 : 100

The adsorption of hydrogen was carried out as described previously², in a volumetric gas adsorption apparatus. The heats of adsorption were calculated from the isotherms at temperatures specified in Table I.

TABLE I—COMPARISON OF HEATS OF MOLECULAR CHEMISORPTION COMPUTED ON CFSO-BEBO MODEL* AND BY ISOSTERIC METHOD ON NICKEL CATALYSTS C AND D

Catalyst	Heats of absorption, Cals/Mole	
	on CFSO-BEBO Model	Isosteric Method
C. Nickel-thoria-kieselguhr	3.2 to 3.8	3.6 to 4.4
D. Nickel-thoria-chromium oxide-kieselguhr.	,,	6.4 to 7.1

* Values calculated at bond order $\eta_{H-H} = 0.116$ (or H-H distance = 1.737 Å) and $\eta = 0$ on the basis of Ni-Ni bond energy⁵ of 34.2 k.cal/mole.

The heats of adsorption calculated theoretically by the CFSO-BEBO model for hydrogen on nickel are given in Table 1. Nickel was assumed to have a structure isoelectronic with platinum ($3d^7 4sp^2$, with e_g and t_{2g} adsorption sites) and of the same symmetry as platinum. The separation between 2e_g and $2t_{2g}$ sites on nickel (111) is 2.48 Å (compared with 2.77 Å for platinum) and the separation between an e_g and an t_{2g} site of nickel is 1.44 Å (as against 1.60 Å for platinum)⁵.

The agreement between the values, in the case of catalyst C); is good considering the assumptions involved viz., (a) the Ni-Ni distances are the same in the catalyst as in pure metal, (b) the heat² of physical adsorption of hydrogen on nickel is 18 k.cals/mole i.e., same as on Pt. It is however, too much to expect a close agreement in the case of the more composite Catalyst D.

Note :

The views expressed in this short note are those of the author, and not of the Institute.

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Infrared Spectral Studies of Solid Solutions of Lead Hydroxylapatite with Arsenate

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LEAD hydroxylapatite, (PbHA), $Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ is very important among the apatite series of compounds¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic substitution reactions¹. The isomorphous replacement of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ by $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ in PbHA results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of PbHA with arsenate according to the following equation

As a part of a series of physico-chemical investigations on the samples the present work deals with the infrared spectral studies of these samples.

Experimental

The details of preparation and characterisation of the samples were reported earlier². The samples used for infrared studies were acetone, washed and air dried. The i-r tracing was carried on Carl-Zeiss Jena UR 10 Double beam instrument in Nujol-mull medium.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples by the method specially worked out³ were given in the Table 1. From the analytical data the molecular

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL DATA OF LEAD HYDROXYLAPATITE AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sam- ple No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	g.atom ratio Pb P+As
	Pb	P	As		
1.	77.45	6.95	—	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$	1.68
2.	76.26	5.82	2.49	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{5.1}(AsO_4)_{0.9}(OH)_2$	1.67
3.	75.04	4.61	5.14	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{4.1}(AsO_4)_{1.9}(OH)_2$	1.67
4.	73.75	3.31	8.01	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{3.0}(AsO_4)_{3.0}(OH)_2$	1.67
5.	72.85	2.40	10.02	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{2.2}(AsO_4)_{3.8}(OH)_2$	1.68
6.	71.52	0.11	13.56	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{1.0}(AsO_4)_{5.0}(OH)_2$	1.68
7.	70.46	—	15.31	$Pb_{10}(AsO_4)_6(OH)_2$	1.68

formula of each sample was calculated and the molar gram atomic ratios of $\frac{Pb}{As+P}$ of each of the sample was calculated and found to have the value ~ 1.68 (theoretical 1.67). The i-r runs of a representative set of the samples (Sl. No. 1, 3, 5, 7 of Table 1) were given in Fig. 1. The lead hydroxylapatite and

Fig. 1. Infrared Spectra of solid solution of Lead hydroxylapatites in the range between 400–1200 cm^{-1} (A, B, C, D spectra corresponds to the spectra of the samples No. 1, 3, 5, 7 of Table 1).

its solid solutions have hexagonal crystalline structure⁴ and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry selection rules due to the influence of site symmetry. The ideal symmetry of tribasic phosphate and/or arsenate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of T_d point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν_4 (570 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (1075 cm^{-1}) of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples (Fig. 1) it could be seen that the ν_3 and ν_4 frequencies corresponding to phosphate ion are shifted to lower frequencies and the shape of the peaks was being effected by the introduction of $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ into the samples. From the consideration of the peak shifts and alteration of peak length ratios one can infer that the phosphate structure is effected by the introduction of $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ into the samples. The shift of the ν_3 and ν_4 of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass. In Barnes expression⁵

$$V = \frac{1}{2\pi c} \sqrt{\frac{K}{\mu}}$$